

Glimpses of Chemical Research of Acharya Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray[†] “...Tribute of a Grand-Student”

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Abstract : Only three aspects, viz., isomorphism and chemical homology, mercurous nitrite and coordination compounds of platinum metals and gold, out of Acharya Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray's diverse interests in chemical research, were briefly reviewed.

Keywords : P. C. Ray, isomorphism and chemical homology, mercurous nitrite, metal-metal bonding, ambivalent Pt, Ir and Au.

Introduction

Acharya Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray, *the founding father of modern chemistry and chemical industry in India*, had varied research interests ranging from isomorphism and chemical homology, chemical analysis of Indian food stuff, through oxides and oxy acids of nitrogen and their metal derivatives, organo nitro compounds and nitrates, organo thio compounds and their metal derivatives, heterocyclic compounds, fluorination of organic compounds, to electrochemistry, thermodynamic and kinetic aspects of chemical reactions and finally coordination chemistry, particularly on varying valences of platinum metals and gold. Of these, only three areas, viz., isomorphism and chemical homology – the area of his first research interest, which earned him his D.Sc. Degree from Edinburgh University (1887), his epoch making discovery of mercurous nitrite, that made him famous among the World chemists as the *Master of nitrites* and coordination compounds of ambivalent platinum metals and gold, his last research interest, were briefly reviewed in this article.

Isomorphism and Chemical Homology : During the time of Ray's D.Sc. research work at the University of Edinburgh, periodic classification of elements based on *Mendeleeff's periodic law* (1869) was the hottest research topic. Naturally, his mentor Professor Alexander Crum Brown induced young Ray to venture into this area. On literature survey, Ray came across a research paper (Kope, *Ann*, 1840) reporting the preparation and characteriza-

tion of double sulfates of the type : $[A_2SO_4.BSO_4.6H_2O + A'SO_4.B'SO_4.6H_2O]$, where, A, A' = alkali metal ions and B, B' = alkaline earth metal ions, with a conclusion that '*vitriolic sulfates have comparable molecular volumes*'. This prompted young Ray to predict his theory of chemical homology, "Simple salts of comparable molecular volumes should form mixed crystals in all proportions"¹.

Neither the electron was discovered nor was the structure of the atom known during those days. Just from the closeness of atomic weights of the metallic elements like V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn (the 3d transition metals as these are known today), Ray thought that the corresponding the M^{2+} ions should have comparable ionic volumes and so their sulfates salts should form mixed crystals in all proportions. From comparable enthalpies of neutralization of dilute solutions of the alkali hydroxides, viz., NaOH, KOH and tetraalkylammonium hydroxides, $[R_4N^+](OH^-)$, tetraalkylphosphonium hydroxides, $[R_4P^+](OH^-)$ and trialkylsulfonium hydroxides, $[R_3S^+](OH^-)$, with dilute solutions of strong acids, Ray concluded all these bases to be equally strong and predicted that their sulfate salts viz., Na_2SO_4 , K_2SO_4 and $[R_4N]_2SO_4$, $[R_4P]_2SO_4$ and $[R_3S]_2SO_4$ should form similar double salts in all proportions. Based on these ideas, Ray prepared and characterized a large number of double sulfates of the general formula :

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derived from the M^{2+} ions of copper-magnesium group and earned his D.Sc. Degree from Edinburgh University (1887).

Ray's interest in chemical homology, however, continued and his research group isolated and characterized² a large number of double sulfates with trialkylsulfonium sulfates and tetraalkylphosphonium sulfates :

$$x = 1, 2; y = 6-8, 10, 11$$

$$x = 1, 2; (y, z) = (0, 1), (1, 1), (1, 2) \text{ and } (2, 2)$$

(M = Fe, Zn, Cd, Mg, Mn, Co, Ni;

R = CH₃, C₂H₅)

A test of meticulousness of Ray and coworkers' experimental designs could be sensed from their experiments for determining the hydration numbers of these double salts. Since thermal dehydration of these double salts at ~105–110°C would lead to the loss of both H₂O and R₃P (or R₂S), they adopted a novel alternative method for the determination of water of hydration in these compounds. The amount of total sulfate was first determined as usual, then the double salts were thermally decomposed to obtain the corresponding divalent metal oxides, M^{II}O, from which the weights of M^{II}SO₄ were calculated. The difference : [(weight of total sulfate) – (weight of M^{II}SO₄)] gave the weight of tetraalkyl phosphonium or trialkyl sulfonium sulfate. Finally, the weight of H₂O was obtained from : [(total weight) – (weight of M^{II}SO₄) – (weight of (R₄P)₂SO₄ or (R₃S)₂SO₄)]. Chemical homology of [(H₃C)₃S⁺], [(H₅C₂)₃S⁺] and [(H₅C₂)₄P⁺] ions with Na⁺, K⁺ and NH₄⁺ ions could be established from similarities in solubility and hygroscopic nature of the double salts derived from these tetraalkyl phosphonium and trialkyl sulfonium sulfates with their Na⁺, K⁺ and NH₄⁺ analogues.

From Goldschmidt (1926) and the Pauling (1927, 1928) radii of various ions, Ray identified some chemically different ions of comparable size, viz., Be²⁺, P⁵⁺ and S⁶⁺ were almost of same size (0.34–0.35 Å) as were O²⁻ and F⁻ ions (1.32–1.33 Å)³. He predicted that fluoroberyllate (BeF₄²⁻) ion and sulfate (SO₄²⁻) ion should

be almost of same ionic volume. Similarly, sulfate (SO₄²⁻) ion and monofluorophosphate (PO₃F²⁻) ion should be isostructural and isoelectronic⁴. Therefore, the simple salts, M^I₂SO₄, M^I₂BeF₄ and M^I₂PO₃F (where, M^I = K⁺, NH₄⁺) should have comparable molar volumes and should form mixed crystals. These predictions were subsequently experimentally verified by Ray and collaborators^{4,5} through isolation and characterization of following isomorphous salts :

where, M^I = K⁺, NH₄⁺, M^{I'} = [(H₃C)₃S⁺], [(H₅C₂)₃S⁺] and [(H₅C₂)₄P⁺]; M^{II} = Mg, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn; (X/Y/Z) = (SO₄²⁻), (BeF₄²⁻) and (PO₃F²⁻) and n = 5, 6, 7. Crystallographic constants of these double sulfates, fluoroberyllates and monofluorophosphates were also comparable. From these observations, Ray concluded, "Ability to form mixed crystals, homomorphism and identity of chemical formula are not necessary coexistent"³, which stood as a modification of Mitscherlich's law of isomorphism (1819), pronouncing isomorphism and mixed crystal formation among the compounds with similar chemical formula. Ray formulated the following generalizations from these studies : (i) Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, [R₄N⁺], [R₄P⁺], and [R₃S⁺] ions were chemically homologous, (ii) [SO₄²⁻], [BeF₄²⁻] and [PO₃F²⁻] ions were isoelectronic and isostructural, (iii) mixed crystals formation required sufficiently close molecular volumes of the simple salts (within ~10% tolerance), (iv) polarizability of oxygen (O²⁻) ion remained the same as given by refraction of crystalline oxides, (v) fundamental vibration frequencies of AX₄ (e.g., SO₄, ClO₄, SiO₄) were accountable by molecular models, (vi) all linkages were ionic. Use of the terms like, molecular volume, molar refraction, polarizability, molecular models, ionic linkage, isoelectronic, isostructural, vibration frequency, etc., in these articles showed a smooth transition of chemistry from the pre electron era of isomorphism and chemical homology to the modern era based on electronic concepts.

Mercurous Nitrite : Like all other discoveries, Ray's discovery of mercurous nitrite had been quite unintentional. In the process of preparing *calomel*, i.e., mercurous chloride (Hg_2Cl_2), required for fabricating a *calomel electrode* for some electrochemical experiment for one of his research scholars, Ray attempted to dissolve mercury in dilute nitric acid to obtain a solution of mercurous nitrate, which on treatment with dilute hydrochloric acid, was supposed to precipitate the sparingly soluble mercurous chloride. On addition of dilute (16–23%) nitric acid to a pool of pure mercury at ordinary temperature ($\sim 22\text{--}32^\circ\text{C}$), he noticed with great surprise, the formation of lovely yellow needle shaped crystals on the surface of the mercury. Not much was known in those days about the reactions of mercury with nitric acid, although, *Feremmy's Encyclopedie Chimique* and *Watt's Dictionary of Chemistry* referred *Marignac salt*⁶, which was basic mercurous nitrate, described by following compositions :

Formation of a basic salt in such an acidic medium appeared as an unusual phenomenon to Ray. On keeping the yellow crystals in contact with the mother liquor, the yellow colour gradually discharged, producing a transparent white mass, composition of which varied with the concentration of nitric acid and temperature. Ray then separated the yellow needles from the mother liquor immediately after their formation and analyzed. Evolution of N_2 gas in the molar ratio, $[2\text{NO}_2^-(aq) = 2\text{N}_2(g)]$ along with CO_2 gas on boiling an aqueous solution of known amount of the yellow crystals with urea, in conformity with the reaction :

confirmed the presence of two moles of nitrite ion per mol of the salt.

On boiling known amount of the yellow crystals with water, the compound decomposed, precipitating black metallic mercury (Hg^0), at the same time producing mercuric ion (Hg^{2+}) in the solution in $[\text{Hg}_2^{2+} : \text{Hg}^0 : \text{Hg}^{2+}] = (1 : 1 : 1)$ molar proportion, in conformity with the reaction :

representing disproportionation of mercurous ion. From the results : $\text{Hg}^0 : \text{Hg}^{2+} : \text{N}_2 (\equiv 2\text{NO}_2^-) = 1 : 1 : 2$, Ray formulated the yellow needles as, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$, i.e., mercurous nitrite^{7–10}. The mother liquor, after separation of the yellow needles, on the other hand, responded to tests for Hg^{2+} , Hg_2^{2+} , NO_3^- and NO_2^- ions and on standing for an hour, triclinic crystals of mercurous nitrite monohydrate, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, separated, which Ray structurally characterized by X-ray measurement (in collaboration with Dr. T. H. Holland, of Geological Survey of India, Calcutta)⁹. But, instead of immediately separating the yellow needles from the mother liquor, if the entire reaction mixture was allowed to stand, the yellow colour of the crystals disappeared gradually and colourless transparent crystals separated out, which responded to tests for Hg_2^{2+} and NO_3^- ions and were subsequently identified to be similar to Marignac salt, reported earlier⁶. Ray's group later applied mercurous nitrite for preparing aliphatic nitro compounds (R-NO_2 , where, R = methyl, ethyl, isopropyl, isoamyl, etc.) from alkyl halides^{11–13}. In this respect mercurous nitrite behaved similar to silver nitrite.

Although mercurous ion was susceptible to disproportionation in basic solution and so was the nitrite ion in acidic solution, one need not be worried about the thermodynamic feasibility of formation of mercurous nitrite. Potts and Allred¹⁴ (USA, 1966) prepared a large number of mercury(I) compounds, but they failed to isolate mercurous nitrite, however, they observed that, *scarcity of mercury(I) compounds was not the result of weak bonding ability of mercury(I) but from the very strong bonding ability of mercury(II). Mercury(I) may form stable complexes with amines of low basicity.* A perusal of Latimer diagram of mercury¹⁵ :

would reveal that disproportionation of Hg_2^{2+} ion in acid medium would not be a thermodynamically favoured process, since the associated Gibbs free energy change (ΔG°) would be positive, as $E_{21}^\circ (+0.920 \text{ volt}) > E_{10}^\circ (+0.789 \text{ volt})$.

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta G^\circ &= (\Delta G^\circ_R - \Delta G^\circ_L) = -n F \Delta E^\circ \\ &= -n F(E^\circ_R - E^\circ_L) = -n F(E^\circ_{10} - E^\circ_{21}) \\ &= (-) 1 \times 96500 \times (-0.131) \text{ volt.coulomb.mol}^{-1} \\ &= +3.02 \text{ k.cal.mol}^{-1}\end{aligned}$$

Very small value of the equilibrium constant (K) of disproportionation of Hg_2^{2+} :

$$\text{Hg}_2^{2+} = \text{Hg}^{2+} + \text{Hg}^\circ \quad E^\circ = (-) 0.131\text{v}$$

$$K = [\text{Hg}^{2+}]/[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] = \sim 6.1 \times 10^{-3}$$

would suggest negligible disproportionation of Hg_2^{2+} ion in acid medium^{16,17}. The potentials in the Latimer diagram of mercury shown above would clearly indicate that Hg° could be oxidized exclusively to Hg_2^{2+} by oxidizing agents having their E° values in the range $+0.789\text{v}$ to $+0.854\text{v}$. Since no common oxidant would meet this requirement, mercury, on treating with excess of an oxidizing agents, would be entirely oxidized to Hg^{II} . However, in presence of at least 50% excess of metallic mercury, only Hg^{I} state would result, since Hg° would readily reduce Hg^{2+} to Hg_2^{2+} . Such a condition prevailed during Ray's experiment, as dilute HNO_3 was added to a pool of metallic mercury, not the reverse. The equilibrium constant (K) would also reveal that, an aqueous solution of a Hg_2^{2+} salt at equilibrium would contain only $\sim 0.6\%$ of Hg^{2+} and the balance of the above disproportionation equilibrium would be easily displaced towards right, in presence of any reagent that would lower the concentration of Hg^{2+} more than Hg_2^{2+} ion, either by forming a more stable complex with Hg^{II} or by precipitating a sparingly soluble Hg^{II} compound (*viz.*, S^{2-} , OH^- , CN^- , I^- , NH_3 , acetyl acetone, *etc.*)¹⁷.

Because of comparatively lower solubility of mercuric hydroxide, $\text{Hg}(\text{OH})_2$, (pK_{sp} 25.5), relative to that of mercurous hydroxide, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{OH})_2$, (pK_{sp} 22.8)^{18,19}, Hg_2^{2+} ion would disproportionate in presence of even traces of alkali or ammonia, because, in neutral or weakly acidic solution, ($5.5 < \text{pH} < 6.5$), mercuric hydroxide would precipitate, but mercurous ions would remain in solution. Consequently, the $[\text{2Hg}^{2+}/\text{Hg}_2^{2+}]$ redox couple ($E^\circ_{21} = +0.920 \text{ volt}$) would transform to $[\text{2Hg}(\text{OH})_2/\text{Hg}_2^{2+}, 4\text{OH}^-]$ couple, having its formal potential, $E^\circ_{21} \leq +0.4 \text{ volt}$ ²⁰ [*i.e.*, lower than E°_{10} ($+0.789 \text{ volt}$)], as a result of which, Hg_2^{2+} ion would disproportionate. However, disproportionation of mercurous ion would be negligible below pH 5.5.

Basicity of nitrite (NO_2^-) ion could be ascertained from ionization constant of nitrous acid (HNO_2). Ray and co-workers²¹ generated nitrous acid *in situ* by treating an aqueous solution of barium nitrite with known amount of standard dilute sulfuric acid solution in the cold :

so that the concentration of HNO_2 could be directly obtained from the amount of sulfuric acid added. They studied the kinetics of decomposition of nitrous acid by conductance method²¹, and found that the rate of its decomposition (*i.e.*, disproportionation) :

was first order in HNO_2 and remained within the range $(1.4 \sim 5.7) \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec.}^{-1}$ in the temperature range $0\text{--}40^\circ\text{C}$. As the product HNO_3 was a much stronger acid than HNO_2 , conductance of the solution slowly increased with time. But, during the course of 180 minutes at 0°C , molar conductance ($\Lambda_{M/32L}$) of nitrous acid solution increased only by 2%, indicating almost negligible decomposition at this temperature. Highest attainable concentration of HNO_2 was 0.185M and the molar ratio of $\text{HNO}_2 : \text{HNO}_3$ was found to be 15.1 : 1. Ray and co-workers²¹ also determined the pK^{H} value of HNO_2 ($\sim 3.3\text{--}3.4$), which was not only close to the literature values^{22,23}, but also more precised and reliable. Thus, an equimolar mixture of HNO_2 and NaNO_2 would be weakly acidic ($\text{pH} \sim 3.3\text{--}3.4$) and even an $\text{HNO}_2 : \text{NaNO}_2 = 1 : 10$ mixture would remain so ($\text{pH} \sim 4.3\text{--}4.4$), at which mercurous ion would not disproportionate. But, as a salt of a weak acid with a strong base, NaNO_2 alone would produce an alkaline solution in water, as for example, pH of an 1M solution of sodium nitrite would be ~ 8.7 , at which mercurous ion would definitely disproportionate. Thus, the failure of Potts and Allred¹⁴ to obtain mercurous nitrite by treating a mercurous salt solution with sodium nitrite might be the outcome of a faulty procedure, it would be improper to infer the non existence of mercurous nitrite from such an observation.

In the dilute acidic (HNO_3) medium and in presence of large excess of metallic mercury, as prevailed under Ray's experimental conditions, Hg_2^{2+} was unlikely to disproportionate. On the other hand, ionization of HNO_2 , resulting from reduction of HNO_3 by mercury, although, would remain greatly suppressed due to common ion effect

by H^+ ion derived from fully ionized HNO_3 , but the prevailing NO_2^- ion concentration would be sufficient enough to effect crystallization of mercurous nitrite. During 1980's two other groups of scientists (English, Rhome and Shutte, from South Africa, 1985)²⁴ and (Ohba, Matsumoto, Mokato and Saito, from Japan, 1986)²⁵ not only prepared mercurous nitrite by following Ray's method, but also structurally characterized the compound by X-ray diffraction measurements. Very recently Samanta, Goswami and Chakravorty (India, 2011)²⁶ isolated the yellow needle shaped crystals of mercurous nitrite, $Hg_2(NO_2)_2$ (1) and white crystals of basic mercurous nitrate, $Hg_6(OH)_2(NO_3)_4$ (2) following Ray's procedure and structurally characterized them by single crystal X-ray diffraction measurements (1 at 100K and 2 at 293K). All these three groups of scientists²⁴⁻²⁶ established the centrosymmetric structure for mercurous nitrite, $Hg_2(NO_2)_2$ (1) involving unsymmetrical nitrite chelation, that is consistent with hybridization of the Hg^I-Hg^I bond and weak intramolecular $Hg^I \cdots O$ interactions (Figs. 1a and b)²⁶.

Fig. 1. (a) : Molecular view of discrete $Hg_2(NO_2)_2$ and (b) : Molecular view of $Hg_2(NO_2)_2$ showing intramolecular interactions [Reproduced from Reference²⁶, S. Samanta, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2011, Section A, Vol. 50, p.138 with permission from CSIR-NISCAIR, New Delhi, India].

Although Potts and Allred¹⁴ failed in their attempt to isolate mercurous nitrite, but in the same paper they rightly observed that, *for mercurous nitrite to exist, the nitrite ion should be bonded to the Hg^I through the oxygen atom, i.e., as nitrito- rather than to the nitrogen atom, as nitro-*. For a stable Hg^I compound, a linear ($O-Hg^I-Hg^I-O$) group would be a very common feature¹⁷. Both these propositions were proved to be true from these recent findings²⁴⁻²⁶.

Samanta, Goswami and Chakravorty²⁶, in addition, identified a basic mercurous nitrate of the formula, $Hg_6(OH)_2(NO_3)_4$ (2), as a homologue ($n = 2$) of the parent compound, $Hg_2\{(OH)Hg_2\}_n(NO_3)_{(n+2)}$. In its centrosymmetric zig-zag structure (Figs. 2a and b), each OH group formed bridge between two mercurous moieties and pairs of nitrate ions were capping the terminal Hg^I atoms with intramolecular $Hg^I \cdots O$ interactions.

Fig. 2. (a) : Molecular view of discrete $Hg_6(OH)_2(NO_3)_4$ and (b) : Molecular view of $Hg_6(OH)_2(NO_3)_4$ showing intramolecular interactions [Reproduced from Reference²⁶, S. Samanta, S. Goswami and A. Chakravorty, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2011, Section A, Vol. 50, p. 139 with permission from CSIR-NISCAIR, New Delhi, India].

A partial list of mercurous compounds taken from *Merk Index (8th edn.)*, Merk & Co., 1968 and *The C. R. C. Handbook of Chemistry and Physics (78th edn.)*, D. L. Lide and H. P. R. Frederiske (eds.), C. R. C. Press, 1998, and published electronically (URL: <http://antoine.frostberg.edu/chem/senese/101/inorganic/faq/missing-mercurous-compounds.shtml>) in *General Chemistry. On Line : F. A. Q. Introduction to Inorganic Chem-*

istry, among other mercurous compounds, included mercury(I) nitrite, of formula, $\text{Hg}_2(\text{NO}_2)_2$, as a yellow solid compound, decomposing on exposure to heat (100 °C) and water. Mercurous nitrite or mercury(I) nitrite (German : *quecksilber(I)-nitrit*) had also been included in the 5th revised and expanded edition, 1997, pp. 530, of *Routledge German Dictionary of Chemistry and Chemical Technology* (German-English), Langenscheidt Fachverlag GmbH, Berlin, ISBN : 0-415-17128-8.

These recent findings²⁴⁻²⁶ on mercurous nitrite would once again reaffirm Ray's original observations⁷⁻¹⁰. Therefore, one's failure to isolate a compound, should not indicate its nonexistence. Failure of a theoretical calculation involving chosen parameters to account for the feasibility of a well characterized real compound, obviously would indicate the interplay of wrong assumptions, faulty data, or some other forms of error. Disproof of a scientific finding without experimental verification and consultation of existing literature would be an act of ignorance.

Discovery of mercurous nitrite by Ray had been an important event in nitrite chemistry. It was in fact the first compound discovered by an Indian chemist working in India and published in foreign journals. Ray's findings were very well acclaimed and corroborated by various laboratories abroad. Through this discovery, not only Ray became famous among the World's chemists as *The Master of Nitrites*, but also the research findings of the Indian chemists working in British ruled India earned International recognition.

Coordination Compounds : Alfred Werner, *The father of coordination chemistry*, prepared and characterized a large number of a new class of transition metal compounds of complex nature having chemical and physical properties and structures quite different from the simple compounds they were composed of. Such differences could hardly be explained on the basis of existing knowledge on structure and bonding. This prompted Werner to postulate his revolutionary *theory of coordination compounds* (1893), which earned him the Chemistry Nobel Prize (1913). Since then, inorganic chemists, all over the World, became immensely interested in this new fascinating field and made significant and useful contributions. Obviously, Ray's group also was no exception. Ray and coworkers isolated and characterized quite a good number of inter-

esting coordination compounds of platinum group metals and gold, with sulfur donor ligands in particular.

But, while assigning structures to some of their compounds on the basis of Werner's postulates, Ray noticed some inadequacies therein. As for example, of the five different compounds : (a) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, (b) $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$, (c) $\text{PtCl} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$, (d) $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and (e) $\text{PtCl}_5 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, obtained on treating chloroplatinic acid, $\text{H}_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$, with diethyl sulfide, Et_2S , structures of only two compounds, (a) and (b), could be described on the basis of Werner's postulates, but, not those of (c)-(e). Ray attempted to explain the properties and structures of these compounds on the basis of varying valences of the metallic element. Empirical formula weight (320.5) of (c) $\text{PtCl} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}$, was almost half its experimental molecular weight (648), determined by ebullioscopy in chloroform solution, suggesting a double formula : $2[\text{PtCl} \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{S}]$, requiring 641. Being unable to describe its structure on the basis of Werner's postulates, Ray proposed a dimeric structure (3), for this compound, involving Pt...Pt bonding, a concept, not pronounced in Werner's postulates.

Ray published this work with the heading, "*Varying Valence of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles. Part-IV. The Inadequacy of Werner's Theory to explain Certain Anomalous Cases*"²⁷. It was possibly for the first time that a metal-metal bonding in coordination compounds was proposed, which subsequently gave birth to large number of such compounds of the platinum group metals. Metal-metal bonded cluster compounds formed one of the most fascinating areas of coordination chemistry today. Linear stacks of $[\text{Pt}(\text{en})\text{Cl}_2]$ molecules, where, (en = ethylenediamine), involving Pt...Pt bonding had now become text book matters²⁸.

Distinguished coordination chemist, Tschugaeff²⁹, suggested a salt-like formula $[\text{Pt}(\text{Et}_2\text{S})_4]^{2+}[\text{PtCl}_6]^{2-}$ for the compound $\text{PtCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (d). Ray on the other hand, isolated and characterized two different compounds : $\text{Pt}^{\text{II}}\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (A) and $\text{Pt}^{\text{IV}}\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ (B) from its alcoholic solution. But neither (A) nor (B) responded to tests

for chloride ion and both were non-electrolytes. Ray formulated compound (d) as a mixed valence molecular compound : $\{(A).(B)\}$ i.e., $\{[Pt^{II}Cl_2.(Et_2S)_2].[Pt^{IV}Cl_4.(Et_2S)_2]\}$, involving linking of square planar Pt^{II} with octahedral Pt^{IV} through extended linear $[...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...]$ bonding, with $2[PtCl_3.2Et_2S]$ as the repeating unit. An insoluble substance of the formula, $PtCl_3.Es_2$, resulting from the reaction of $H_2[PtCl_6]$ with the 1,4-disulfide, $(Et-S-CH_2CH_2-S-Et)$, abbreviated as ES_2 , did not respond to tests for Cl^- ion and was identified as a molecular compound of $[Pt^{II}(ES_2)Cl_2]$ and $[Pt^{IV}(ES_2)Cl_4]$ ³⁰. Its insolubility in all ordinary solvents could be due to its infinite chain polymeric structure consisting of linear stacks of square planar $[Pt^{II}(ES_2)Cl_2]$ and octahedral $[Pt^{IV}(ES_2)Cl_4]$ involving $[...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...]$ chains with $2[PtCl_3.Es_2]$ as the repeating unit. *Wolfram's red salt*, with octahedral $[Pt^{IV}(EtNH_2)_4Cl_2]^{2+}$ and square planar $[Pt^{II}(EtNH_2)_4]^{2+}$ ions linked in $[...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...]$ chains in its structure and the other four Cl^- ions remaining within the lattice²⁸ was one of the best known compounds of this type. These types of compounds showed high electrical conductivity along the direction of $[...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...Pt^{II}...Cl-Pt^{IV}-Cl...]$ chains.

Ray and his group isolated and analytically characterized series of poly nuclear platinum compounds³¹⁻³³ of general formulae :

$$x = 3-13, y = 2-10, z = 1-2, n = 0, 8;$$

$$x = 2-10, y = 1-9, z = 1-3;$$

where, **B** = base, such as, methyl amine, ethyl amine, propyl amine, benzyl amine, pyridine, quinoline, etc., and proposed zig-zag chain structures involving the $[... = Pt = S-S = Pt = S-S = ...]$ moiety as the repeating unit, with each of the two terminal Pt atoms coordinated by one halide ion and a base. With proper bond angles at the sp^2 hybridized sulfur atoms, such structures would appear like helical chains (4a). From close proximity of the platinum atoms in these structures, the possibility of extended $(...Pt...Pt...)$ bonding of the type, (4b) could not be ruled out. The possibility of one dimensional electrical conductance for these materials could be a subject of investigation by modern techniques.

Experimental molecular weight the compound, $PtCl(Et-S-S-Et)$, was three times its empirical formula weight. This prompted Ray to suggest a trimeric formula :

$[PtCl(Et-S-S-Et)]_3$ and a macro cyclic ring structure (5a) for this complex³⁴⁻³⁶. Close proximity of three platinum atoms in this structure would suggest a novel closed type three-centered $(...Pt...Pt...Pt...)$ bonding (5b), subject to investigation by modern techniques.

Affinity of platinum for sulfur donor atoms was fur-

ther demonstrated from the reaction of platinum chloride, PtCl_4 , with sodium dithioethylene glycol, $(\text{HS}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-\text{SH})$ in acetone, producing two compounds, $[\text{Pt}(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{S})_2]$ (7) and $[\text{Pt}_2(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{S})_5]$ (8), by replacement of the halogen atoms. Ray interpreted (7) and (8) respectively as compounds of tetra- and penta-valent platinum³⁴ :

From the reactions of $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{IrCl}_6]$ with dialkyl sulfides (R_2S , $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) Ray's group isolated a series of compounds³⁷⁻³⁹ : (a) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{R}_2\text{S}$, (b) $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{R}_2\text{S}$ and (c) $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{R}_2\text{S}$. From its insolubility in ionizing solvents, Ray proposed $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{R}_2\text{S}$ (a) to be a molecular compound. Preserving the hexa-coordination of iridium, this compound could be represented by two alternative dimeric formulae, viz., $[(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2(\text{Cl})_3\text{Ir}^{\text{III}} \cdots \text{Ir}^{\text{III}}(\text{Cl})_3(\text{SR}_2)_2]$ involving $(\text{Ir} \cdots \text{Ir})$ bonding or $[(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2(\text{Cl})_2\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2\text{Ir}(\text{Cl})_2(\text{SR}_2)_2]$ involving two bridging Cl^- ligands. Similarly, $\text{Ir}_2\text{Cl}_5 \cdot 4\text{R}_2\text{S}$ (c) could be described by a $(\mu\text{-Cl})_3$ bridged mixed valence ($\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}, \text{Ir}^{\text{II}}$) formulation : $[(\text{R}_2\text{S})_2(\text{Cl})\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})_3\text{Ir}(\text{Cl})(\text{SR}_2)_2]$.

Ray's group identified the orange and the red varieties of $\text{IrCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{R}_2\text{S}$ (b) as *cis*- and *trans*-isomers (9a, 9b) respectively. The *trans*-isomer (9b), crystallized from chloroform as a red compound, was efflorescent in nature, which rapidly and spontaneously transformed to a reddish white opaque mass. This caused extreme difficulty in its analytical characterization^{38,39}. Ray, due to his failing health in those days, was compelled to remain physically detached from laboratory works. The concerned research fellow was in great hesitation to bother his *Guruji*

with this problem, but finally had to do so as the *Guruji* himself inquired about the findings. On hearing the fact from his disciple, Ray immediately suggested, "*The compound (9b) possibly crystallized with a molecule of chloroform of crystallization. Rapid and spontaneous loss of chloroform at ordinary temperature, was responsible for the above transformation and the consequent discrepancy in the analytical results*", which was subsequently established.

This fact gave ample evidence of his mental attachment to chemical research despite failing health and physical detachment from day to day laboratory work during the penultimate years of his life.

Ray and coworkers isolated and analytically characterized several compounds of gold with different mercapto ligands⁴⁰⁻⁴². Many of these compounds were described by unusual chemical formulae. Assuming variable oxidation states of the metal, ranging from +1 to +5, they proposed tentative structures of some of these gold complexes.

Treatment of chloroauric acid (HAuCl_4) with diethyl disulfide (Et-S-S-Et) gave a compound of unusual empirical formula, $\text{EtS} \cdot \text{AuCl}_2$. The compound, on molecular weight determination by depression of freezing point method, was identified to be a dimer, $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{AuCl}_2$. Ray proposed two alternative structures (10a and 10b) for this compound involving Au^{II} and Au^{IV} .

Another compound, $\text{Et}_2\text{S}_2 \cdot \text{Au}_4\text{Cl}_2$ (11) was obtained from the reaction of AuCl_3 with diethyl disulfide. Ray assigned this to be a mixed valence compound composed of Au^{II} and Au^{III} .

Reactions of AuCl_3 with dithioethyleneglycol ($\text{HS-CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{-SH}$), under different conditions gave a number of interesting gold compounds, described by the formulae : $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_2\cdot\text{Au}_2\text{Cl}$ (12), $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_5\text{Au}_2$ (13) and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{S}_2)_4\text{Au}_3\text{Cl}$ (14). Ray interpreted (12) as a mixed valence Au^{II} and Au^{III} complex and (13) as a Au^{V} complex, but remarked (14) as a compound of unusual stoichiometry. (14) could, however, be represented as a mixed valence Au^{I} and Au^{IV} compound, having a structure similar to that of (13).

Although the structures of most of these Pt, Ir and Au compounds were proposed out of intuition, without any physicochemical support, and even some of the struc-

tures would appear unusual, nevertheless, majority of these compounds were obtained in crystalline forms, indicating their purity. Further exploration of these Pt, Ir and Au compound with the help of improved methodologies and modern instrumental techniques might be able to unfold many unknown aspects of chemistry of these noble metals. In view of some wonderful physical properties and extensive medicinal applications of some platinum compounds in *cancer chemotherapy*, gold compounds, particularly, use of gold thio compounds in *chrysotherapy*, a revisiting of Ray's works in this area might be a worthy pursuit.

A perusal of Ray's 158 odd research papers⁴³ would reveal wide versatility in his research interests. Venturing to move from one research area to another even of completely unrelated nature, with wonderful ease, great expertise and meticulous design were his novelty. It would be something like a smooth journey from the pre-electron era of isomorphism and chemical homology, through the days electrochemistry, thermodynamics and kinetics, electronic concept of chemical bonding to the days coordination chemistry, isomerism, spectroscopy, structure, stereochemistry, stability and reactivity, metal-metal bonding and cluster compounds.

The great chemist, a kind hearted, benevolent and patriotic Professor, who had become an icon of plain living and high thinking, devoid of any vanity and pride like a *Saint*, often used to say, "*I have no sense of success on any large scale things achieved, but have the sense of having worked and having found happiness in doing so*". His last words, "*I was never a more bonafide student than today*", not only would reflect his unending thrust for knowledge, but also would remain as the last words in science. Coincidence of his 150th Birth Anniversary with the *International Year of Chemistry (2011)* had been a blessing in disguise, which gave all Indian chemists an opportunity to celebrating both the occasions together in an auspicious manner. The author would remain grateful to the Indian Chemical Society for giving him an opportunity to pay tribute to his *Grand-Teacher* through this article. The Royal Society of Chemistry on September 29, 2011, declared Acharya Sir P. C. Ray as the *Father of Indian Chemistry* and honoured his life and works by conferring on him the first ever *Chemical Landmark Plaque* outside Europe.

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